

MCMC

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0.0.1 Effect of surfactants on the thermoresponse of PNIPAM investigated in the brush geometry

Isaac J. Gresham, Joshua D. Willott Edwin C. Johnson, Peixun Li, Grant B. Webber, Erica J. Wanless, Andrew R.J. Nelson, Stuart W. Prescott
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For additional details regarding the use of refnx, see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#).

For additional details regarding the use of the freeform model, or for details regarding the usefulness of MCMC for NR analysis, see the [paper](#)

For additional details regarding MCMC (implimented via emcee), see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#)

For additional details regarding PT-MCMC (implimented via ptemcee), see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#)

To follow this example, run the notebooks in the following order 1. D2O_ModelCreation.ipynb 2. CM_ModelCreation.ipynb 3. MCMC.ipynb

```
[1]: %matplotlib inline
```

```
[8]: import pickle
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.stats import norm, truncnorm
import copy
import warnings

from refnx.reflect import SLD, Slab, ReflectModel, MixedReflectModel
from refnx.dataset import ReflectDataset as RD
from refnx.analysis import Objective, CurveFitter, PDF, Parameter, □
    ↪ process_chain, load_chain

import sys
sys.path.append('./Code')

from FreeformVFP import FreeformVFP
import plottools
# from rednhelpers import background_estimator
```

```

from GenericBrushObjective import make_brush_objective

def unpack_values (values):
    std_norm_bounds = (-1.96,1.96) #https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/1.96
    return values[1], (values[0], values[2]), truncnorm(*std_norm_bounds,
    ↪loc=values[1], scale=(values[2]-values[0])/(2*1.96))

def set_param(params, pname, value):
    for p in params.flattened():
        if p.name == pname:
            if p.vary:
                p.value = p.bounds.valid(value)
                break

def save_diffev_results(fitter, save_dir):
    np.savetxt(f'{save_dir}/diffev_bestparams_{fitter.objective.name}',
    ↪fitter.objective.varying_parameters())
    pickle.dump(fitter.objective, open(f'{save_dir}/diffev_bestobj_{fitter.
    ↪objective.name}.pkl', 'wb'))
    return np.round(fitter.objective.logpost(),2), fitter.objective.
    ↪varying_parameters()

def print_fitqual(objectives):
    for idx, objective in enumerate(objectives):
        red_chisqr = objective.chisqr()/len(objective.data.x)
        print (f"{idx}: {objective.name}, {np.round(objective.logpost())}, {np.
    ↪round(red_chisqr,2)}")

```

```

[3]: # fit_names = ["W10 lowdSDS-CM 25C",      "W10 lowdSDS-CM 40C",
#              "W10 highdSDS-CM 25C",      "W10 highdSDS-CM 40C",
#              "W10 highdC12E5-CM 25C",    "W10 highdC12E5-CM 40C",
#              "W08 highdCTAB-CM 25C",     "W08 highdCTAB-CM 40C"]

# fit_names = ["W10 lowdSDS-d2o 25C", "W10 lowdSDS-d2o 32C", "W10 lowdSDS-d2o
    ↪40C",
#              "W10 highdSDS-d2o 25C", "W10 highdSDS-d2o 32C", "W10
    ↪highdSDS-d2o 40C",
#              "W10 lowdC12E5-d2o 25C", "W10 lowdC12E5-d2o 32C", "W10
    ↪lowdC12E5-d2o 40C",
#              "W10 highdC12E5-d2o 25C", "W10 highdC12E5-d2o 32C", "W10
    ↪highdC12E5-d2o 40C",]

fit_names = ["W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C", "W10 highdC12E5-d2o 40C"]

```

For neatness, you could set the save directory to a subfolder

```
[17]: save_direc = './'
file_prepend = 'diffev_bestobj_'
```

Create fitters based off the objectives created in D2O_ModelCreation.

These could be initialised from the prior (which will discard the optimum found by differential evolution) for an attempt at a global search, or from the covariance matrix at the optima for a local calculation of parameter uncertainties.

After initializing a small number of MCMC steps will be taken. This will generate some warnings, as some of the starting profiles will be impossibly diffuse - these can be ignored.

WARNING: This will overwrite existing fitters saved the the directory with the same name. Once you have created all your fitters and you're just burning CPU time, best to comment out the cell.

```
[18]: for name in fit_names:
    print (name)
    obj = pickle.load(open(f"{save_direc}{file_prepend}{name}.pkl", 'rb'))
    obj.model.threads=1
    fitter = CurveFitter(obj, nwalkers=600, ntemps=10)
    fitter.initialise('prior')
    # fitter.initialise('covar')

    fitter.sample(1, nthin=10, pool=8)

    pickle.dump(fitter, open(f'{name}_fitter.pkl', 'wb'))
```

W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C

```
0%| | 0/10 [00:00<?,
?it/s]/Volumes/GoogleDrive/My Drive/PhD/07 Papers/Surfactants/Paper 1 code
repo./Code/FreeformVFP.py:296: RuntimeWarning: extent > 3000, perfoming refl.
calc on first 3000A.
  warnings.warn('extent > %d, perfoming refl. calc on first %dA.' %
/Volumes/GoogleDrive/My Drive/PhD/07 Papers/Surfactants/Paper 1 code
repo./Code/FreeformVFP.py:296: RuntimeWarning: extent > 3000, perfoming refl.
calc on first 3000A.
  warnings.warn('extent > %d, perfoming refl. calc on first %dA.' %
/Volumes/GoogleDrive/My Drive/PhD/07 Papers/Surfactants/Paper 1 code
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/Volumes/GoogleDrive/My Drive/PhD/07 Papers/Surfactants/Paper 1 code
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/Volumes/GoogleDrive/My Drive/PhD/07 Papers/Surfactants/Paper 1 code
repo./Code/FreeformVFP.py:296: RuntimeWarning: extent > 3000, perfoming refl.
calc on first 3000A.
  warnings.warn('extent > %d, perfoming refl. calc on first %dA.' %
```



```
warnings.warn('extent > %d, performing refl. calc on first %dA.' %  
100%| | 10/10 [00:20<00:00, 2.01s/it]
```

1 Load fitters

```
[20]: fitters = {}  
for fit_name in fit_names:  
    print (fit_name)  
    try:  
        fitter = pickle.load(open(f'{fit_name}_fitter.pkl', 'rb'))  
        print (f'reloaded previous fit for {fit_name} ({fitter.chain.shape}).')  
        fitters[fit_name] = fitter  
    except FileNotFoundError:  
        print (f'failed to load {fit_name}')
```

W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C

reloaded previous fit for W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C ((1, 10, 600, 22)).

W10 highdC12E5-d2o 40C

reloaded previous fit for W10 highdC12E5-d2o 40C ((1, 10, 600, 22)).

Do the MCMC sampling (takes a long time)

```
[19]: NumSamples_target = 40  
  
for name, fitter in fitters.items():  
    to_sample = NumSamples_target - fitter.chain.shape[0]  
    if to_sample < 0:  
        to_sample = 0  
    print (name, to_sample)  
    for i in range(to_sample):  
        print ("%d/%d"%(i+1,to_sample))  
        time.sleep(1)  
        fitter.sample(1, nthin=500, pool=12)  
        time.sleep(1)  
        pickle.dump(fitter, open(name + '_fitter.pkl', 'wb'))
```

```
[ ]:
```